

Native Language Leaked From Ancient Sources...

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Annotation: The concepts of language, nation, society and state are considered historical units that require each other and do not live separately from each other. Hence, under the concepts of the Uzbek language, the Uzbek nation, the Uzbek society and the state of Uzbekistan are aspects of the history of our people, modern life, way of life, spirituality, culture, art, etc., we can be sure that huge treasures associated with this are hidden. Looking back at history, we see that the Uzbek language has gone through a long and difficult path of development.

The Uzbek language appears before our eyes as one of the most powerful, flourishing and beautiful branches of the family tree of the Turkic language; it is embodied as a divine blessing, vividly embodying its sorrows, pains and sufferings.

In this sense, arguing on any issue related to the Uzbek language is tantamount to thinking about the fate of our people, the influence of our native language in our country and in the international arena.

Based on this, this article presented the Uzbek people and the Uzbek language, difficulties, problems and solutions towards giving the Uzbek language the status of the state language.

Keywords: Uzbek language, Uzbek nation, Uzbek society, tribal language, ancestral language, language history, Turkish language, society, state of Uzbekistan, state language, related languages, foreign languages.

Text.

The Uzbek language is one of the oldest Turkic languages due to its wide range of expressive capabilities, grammatical perfection and stylistic diversity. The Turkic (Uzbek) language has always been an elegant literary language, a living spoken language, and one of the main languages on ancient caravan routes...

Khans, emirs and rulers came and went; the riches that they found, the treasures that they collected in a thousand efforts, disappeared without a trace from the scenes of history, priceless palaces cracked, but our native language did not suffer, but on the contrary, it was filled, enriched and expanded as years and eras passed; bent, bent, but did not break.

The great enlightener Abdurauf Fitrat wrote about this at the beginning of the last century: "Which language is the richest and most unfortunate language in the world?" You know? Turkic. I don't want to be a poet, that's true. The richest language in the world is Turkic, and the most unfortunate language is Turkic. The problem of languages is what happened during Soviet times.

The richness of a language is the abundance of words, word formation and accuracy of grammar. In terms of the richness of its vocabulary, breadth of coverage, completeness of rules and originality, our language is not inferior to other eastern languages; in fact, it completely leaves the Persian language behind [Fitrat,

2006, 336].

That's true. Tell us that we are the children of this people and the owners of this language, that we place the Uzbek language above other Turkic languages and that we have raised its honor to the level of Fitrat. The "Turkish" language Fitrat speaks is itself an Uzbek language.

The river of language does not stop, it always flows deep, and everyone takes its share according to their abilities and needs.

"Devonu Lugotit-Turk" by Mahmud Koshgari, "Kutadgu Bilik" by Yusuf Khos Hajib, "Hikmatlar" by Ahmed Yasawi, "Qissasi Rabgazi" by Rabguzi, "Mukhabbatnama" by Khorezmi are rare examples of Turkish literature. The language of such unique works is phonetically, lexically, and grammatically unique, and are stylistically closer to the Uzbek language than other Turkic languages, and accordingly are mentioned among the unique sources of the Uzbek language.

The reason is that the Uzbek people and the Uzbek language (Turkic-Chigatoi language) had their position and influence at the stages of tribe > clan > ulus (nation) > nation, which are historical associations of Turkic peoples. According to sources, the Karluk, Chigil, Argun, Yagmo, Kipchak, Barlos, Kenegas, Dzhaliyir and others tribes who led the Turkic people played an important role in the formation and development of the Uzbek people [Asqarov, 2015, 68].

In accordance with their historical status, they were called Uzbek tribes, Uzbek clans and Uzbek people. Therefore, language is the main symbol of tribe, clan, nation and nation, regardless of its stage.

It is considered natural that whatever language is spoken by the majority of the population living in a certain territory, this language will become a special calling card and seal of the local people - the land of the Uzbeks, the Uzbek people, Uzbek cities, as well as Uzbek villages.

When creating a particular state, special attention is paid to the unity of language along with the unity of political, territorial, customs and values. The language of the nation that has the majority on the territory of this state rightfully has the status of the state language.

For example, Russian in the Russian Federation, English in the United States of America, German in Germany, French in France, Spanish in Colombia, Portuguese in Brazil, Persian in Iran have the status of official languages.

However, depending on the time and conditions in some countries, two or more languages may be considered the official language. English and French are used equally in Canada, Urdu and English in Pakistan, English and French in Kenya, Swahili and English in Tanzania and Uganda, and English and Filipino in the Philippines.

The official languages are English, Irish, Scottish in England, French, Dutch, German in Belgium, German, French, Italian, Romansh in Switzerland, English, Chinese, Malay, Tamil in Singapore.

The official languages of South Africa are 11 languages: English, Afrikaans, Venda, Zulu, Xhosa, Ndebele, Swati, Northern Sotho, Sesotho, Tswana, Tsonga.

The Uzbek language has the status of the state language in two countries of the world: the Republic of Uzbekistan and Afghanistan.

According to Afghan researcher Mohammad Humayun Nadeem, the Turkic-speaking people here are called Turknajot or Turktabors, and they live in 9 provinces located in the north of the country in the Turkestan and Katagan regions. Foreb, Yuvuzhon, Saripul, Balkh, Samangon to the Turkestan region;

The Katagan region includes the regions of Baghlan, Kunduz, Takhar and Badakhshan. The language of the people living in these regions, that is, Uzbek, is considered the 5th state language after English, Urdu, Pashtun and Tajik [Мухаммад Хумаюн. 2022, 49].

As is known, the territory of present-day Central Asia was ruled in the past by the Turanian Kingdom, the Turkic Khanate, the Karakhanids, the Ghaznavids, the Seljuks, the Khorezmid, the Timurid Empire, the

Bukhara Emirate, the Khiva and Kokan Khanates. They included different tribes, clans, peoples, united around one state and one idea.

In these countries, the leading languages are occupied by Arabic, Persian, Turkish and Mongolian. On the other hand, every advanced member of society was fluent in these languages and there were no problems in communication and business between the population.

Therefore, the main criterion for the use and development of languages was justice and linguistic tolerance. For example, Amir Temur in his “Tuzuklari Temur” has under his command a Barlos, Tarkhan, Argun, Jaloir, Barlos, Tarkhan, Argun, Jaloir, Duldai, Suldus.

Emphasizing that he saw 40 ethnic groups, such as the Kipchak, Orlov and Tatar, as equals, he writes: “I showed respect to the nobles of the Turks, Tajiks, Arabs and Ajams from different ranks and tribes who entered my refuge, and I treated the rest to him accordingly. I did good to the good and left the bad to their own evil. Whoever befriended me, I did not forget the value of his friendship and showed him kindness, mercy and honor” [Amir Temur, 1991, 66].

It is clear that on the territory of the huge kingdom built by Amir Temur, a special linguistic environment reigned. We have not received any negative historical information regarding communication barriers. In ancient Turan, Turkestan, no one discriminated against another in linguistic terms; ancient values, firmly held in the process of communication, were passed down from generation to generation for centuries.

As a result of this, there was not a single quarrel over language between the numerous peoples and nationalities living in Central Asia. The Turkish language was revered as an invaluable blessing that unites all Turkic peoples.

In the second half of the 19th century the situation changed. Tsarist Russia occupied Central Asia by military force. A new era has arrived in language policy. The Russian language has taken a leading position. After this, in order to bring it to a new level, the Turkish language was forced to be destroyed from within, to lower its status in society.

Tsarist Russia and its successor, the Soviet government, which with great difficulty acquired territories inhabited by Turkic-speaking peoples, acted farsightedly: they divided the historically united and unique Turkic people into several parts.

In 1924–1936, the Soviet socialist republics of Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Turkmenistan, Azerbaijan and Tajikistan appeared on the world map. As a result, the previously unified Turkish language was divided into approximately 30 languages, such as Uzbek, Kazakh, Kyrgyz, Turkmen, Tatar and Bashkir.

The one-sided nature of this movement can be seen in the fact that until 1924, Uzbekistan, the Turkestan Autonomous Republic, Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan were part of the RSFSR as the Kyrgyz and Kara-Kyrgyz Autonomous Regions.

The Soviets followed their own policies in naming the newly formed republics. It is known from history that the Turkestan Autonomous Republic, which operated as part of the former union from April 30, 1918 to October 27, 1924, in all respects it was desirable to call the Turkestan SSR in the national-territorial delimitation of 1924, but the population is here to alienate. Because of its history and identity, it was called the Uzbek SSR, emphasizing the name of the nation that made up the largest population according to the 1920 census.

At that time, the total population of Turkestan was 5,221,963 people. Of these, 2,050,775 Uzbeks (41.3 percent), 1,091,925 Kazakhs (18.8 percent), 522,292 Kyrgyz (10.0 percent), 399,912 Tajiks (7.7 percent), 266,681 Turkmen (5.1 percent), 75,334 were Karakalpaks (1.4 percent) [[https:// ru.wikipedia.org/wiki](https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki)].

The numerical superiority of the Uzbeks made it possible to call the newly formed republic the Uzbek SSR. Of course, school education, the media, radio-television and official documentation began to be conducted in the Uzbek language.

Those who worked to strengthen the position of the Uzbek language as the state language at that time were: Abdullah Kadiri, Abdulhamid Cholpon, Abdurauf Fitrat, Mahmudhoja Behbudi, and after them Abdullah Kahhor, artists such as Afur Gulam, Oybek, Hamid Olimjon, Zulfiya played a big role.

It is worth noting that modern writers and poets such as Abdulla Oripov, Erikn Vakhidov, Pirmkul Kadyrov, Adil Yagubov and Otkir Gashimov have shown dedication in preserving the position of the Uzbek language as the state language.

According to the famous writer Abdulla Kadiri: “The Uzbek language is not poor, but those who call the Uzbek language poor are poor. “They should not transfer their ignorance to the Uzbek language” is a clear confirmation of our opinion [<https://kh-davron.uz/dir/kutubxona/uzbek/ona-tili>].

Therefore, the government in which that language is used, as well as all citizens living in that country, are equally responsible for the development and progress of a particular language. The status of the main language on the territory of a state is a sign of the sovereignty of the state, its influence in the internal and external spheres, and the moral level of its inhabitants.

In fact, the state is not only a territorial, economic space and transit corridor, but also a cultural space, communication and living space. The state is created for the purpose of preserving and protecting people, cultural values, nature and all natural resources, people and human rights [*Yulo Vooglayd, 2023, 259-260*].

State sovereignty is manifested only when the state takes upon itself the protection of national languages on its territory, especially the main language in which it operates, and determines its status from a legal and regulatory point of view, its influence on the international arena is visible.

Separately, it should be noted that our country was a former union state until 1989. Accordingly, business was conducted primarily in Russian throughout the Union and in Uzbekistan.

All administrative documents, administrative work in government agencies, meetings, meetings and conferences were conducted in Russian. In particular, international relations and diplomatic relations with countries and states were carried out only through the Russian language.

The Uzbek language was one of the languages dependent on the Russian language, as one of the languages of more than 150 peoples that were part of the union. The work even reached such a level that the two-volume “Annotated Dictionary of the Uzbek Language”, published in 1981, was published in Moscow by the Russian Language publishing house.

On the one hand, this should not be surprising, because time demanded it. Everyone had to obey these rules.

The “Perestroika” policy of the mid-1980s, which shocked the world, also awakened the Uzbek people from sleep... The Uzbek people saw their history, values and national identity in the form of their native language and began the first steps of the struggle for independence to obtain state status for the Uzbek language.

A man who found his identity, in whose heart the pain of the people and the nation awakened, rallied and rallied around the Uzbek language. Our native language has become the flag of the nation, the symbol of the nation (!)

The third Renaissance of its development under the slogan “From national revival to national uplift.” It is recognized as one of the countries that has its own national flag, national emblem and national anthem, and occupies a worthy place among more than 200 countries of the world. The role of the Uzbek language in our society is defined in a separate article in our general dictionary: “The state language of the Republic of Uzbekistan is the Uzbek language [*Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Article 4*].

It all comes down to maintaining this status, protecting it from all kinds of disasters and regularly fighting for its honor and reputation

After all, we are all equally responsible for the future of the Uzbek language.

We all know that in recent years the problem of interlingual integration has become more acute. Before the years of independence, we learned new words only from the Russian language and world languages through it, but today new lexical units enter our language directly from English, German, French, Arabic, Ottoman-Turkish languages.

It is worth noting that expressions such as I'm going on vacation, yes, we went to dinner, and help appeared, appeared in our speech.

Bravo – ofarin (well done, blessed), *ok* – hammasi joyida (okey), *ayva* – salom (hello), *super* – eng zo‘r (super), *o kruto* – dabdabali (coll), *shes sekundda yest qilamiz* – we'll eat in six seconds), *sening problemang* – finally a problem, *ishlar joyida* – great job, *telefon zanyat* – phone is busy, *zakaz qildim* – I ordere.

The purity of speech is mainly influenced by the following elements:

1. Pronunciation of words, phrases, as well as grammatical forms, words and phrases characteristic of local dialects and dialects.
2. Inappropriately used foreign words and phrases.
3. Jargons.
4. Vulgarisms.
5. Excessively repeated “parasitic” words in speech.
6. Clericalism.

Their analysis shows that, in particular, foreign words in names are “inserted artificially,” attracting the attention of others, similar to advertising a name.

Uzbek + English or English Uzbek two-component Guliston Grand, Atlas Market, Termez Palace, Aliya Pissa, Ocean Burger, Nilu Buytke; Yes Boss cafe with three or more components, sweet sausage seller, guest house of the Fayz family, Termiz, Tort Ukuk market, Uzbek-Russian + English mini-restaurant “Iskandar”; restaurant “Diplomat”, “Moscow Delicacy”, burger “Nike”, burger “Street”, fast food “Andalus”, the components of which are made up of Russian-international words; This can be clearly observed in names such as Zeytun, Darkhan Doner and Doner Taim, which are derived from Turkish and Arabic.

It's surprising that such words as *grand*, *market*, *palase*, *burger*, *bouytquye*, *Yes Boss*, *guest*, *Hause*, *sity* still have not found a place in our vocabulary?! This is nothing more than the domestication of foreign words, imitation of European models and the desire for foreign naming (advertising) forms.

Construction companies *Arch Desing Servise*, *Termiz Modern Project LLC*; *JSC "ELITA-BAKHROM"*, *LLC "Al Bike Chicken"*, *JSC "Pizza House Termiz"*, *LLC "Sar Al Legro"*, *consumer service organizations*; *We also meet in such hotels as NAT GAZ GROUP LLC*, *MERIDIAN HOTEL LLC*, *MEGA AL QASR LLC*.

Also, mixed names do not suit our language, such as *Restaurant Ideal SS*, *000000market*, *Arbat 75*, *HOT DOG & BON DOG*, *Shashlik & Somsa House*, *Lagmon & Manti bu Sayora*, *Cafe 53 Shiken* (shopping center). Names like *Azlarsoy*, the perfect bird, made up of a combination of simple words, make people melt.

Minimarket Marvarid, Minimarket Yubileiny, Supermarket Yubileiny, Minimarket 5 House, Multimarket, SevSarmarket, Multisupermarket, made with the participation of the word market, is nothing more than a modern design.

Names like *Aigerim*, *Murager*, *Rihiz* do nothing for the development of our language. Names like “*Khan Sultan*” and “*Cafe Karavan*”, written incorrectly in Cyrillic, clearly lead us to illiteracy.

The time has come to limit such names as “Kola Center Gosht”, “Nurli Diyor National Nutrition”.

Conclusion. In general, language is given to man in order to praise God, the Creator, the Universe and the best qualities in it, and spread this among others. Every national language acquires charm and grace when it is properly used within its sphere of influence. Otherwise, it will get dirty, become unusable and end up in a shameful place in the eyes of the owners who carry it.

People who lived in a certain era owe their language to future generations. This debt cannot be canceled by anything. Only attention and a natural “willingness” to use language are the best tools on this path.

Therefore, attention should be paid to the state language, its expedient use everywhere, to avoid artificiality, haste, modernism and imitation, on the contrary, to give appropriate names to enterprises, organizations and institutions. This is a sacred duty.

All our compatriots who washed us and combed our hair white. Good luck to all of us on this journey.

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